

Unveiling the Patterns of Employability in Higher Education: A DBSCAN Cluster Analysis of College Programs

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Abstract

This paper applies DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) clustering to examine patterns in employability across 26 college programs over three years, 2021 to 2023. This study uses secondary data sources on graduate numbers and employability rates to look for possible understructures and groupings among academic programs based on employment outcomes. To reduce the dimensionality, PCA was used while performing DBSCAN based on the values of $\epsilon=0.73$ and $\text{MinPts}=6$, which were derived from k-distance graph analysis. The obtained clusters are then analyzed about measures such as the Silhouette Coefficient of 0.3990, Calinski-Harabasz Index of 12.8237, and Davies-Bouldin Index of 1.0487. The analysis made clear that the divisions of three groups differentiated: large numbers of programs with stable employability rates, relatively small numbers with consistent growth, and outliers with more volatile patterns. This research draws together findings on graduate employability that describe the dynamics across fields of study, which inform targeted interventions and strategic decision-making in higher education. The study contributes to understanding the complex relationship between academic programs and employment outcomes and UN Sustainable Development Goals 4, Quality Education, and 8, Decent Work and Economic Growth. This proposed research develops an evidence-based approach to supporting increasing students' employability and facilitating better connections between higher education and labor markets.

Keywords: *Human Capital Theory, Career EDGE, College Graduate Employability, DBSCAN Cluster, UNSDG 4 and 8.*

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Introduction

Measuring the employability of university graduates a year after graduation is essential because it assesses the effectiveness of the higher education institution in delivering its

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mission and vision (Akkermans et al., 2023). It gives a better understanding of labor market dynamics and paves the way for future educational strategies (Viollaz et al., 2023). Employability is a keystone performance indicator for monitoring HEIs (Castro & Tumibay, 2019). A study indicated that the quality of a university program typically measures graduate employment rates (Roman & Villanueva, 2023), while most interest is focused on how effective the transition of graduates to work within a year post-graduation (Ferri et al., 2022). For instance, the European Council benchmarks employability at 82% three years after graduation for students aged 20 to 34, emphasizing the expectation that HEIs should produce work-ready graduates (Lokmic-Tomkins et al., 2021). This measure is not only a reflection of institutional success but also a determinant of funding and policy decisions concerning higher education (Sharma, 2019; Taffe & Gilpin, 2021).

The gap is where the measurement of employability becomes vital. Studies have shown that employers fill this space due to the need for appropriate skills learned in college and an organization (Akkermans et al., 2023). This gap arises in essential skills relating to emotional intelligence and the career planning required to get a job. Institutions identify these gaps and rectify their curricula to keep up with the needs of employers.

The data on employability is used to guide policymakers and educators on the imperative changes needed in curriculum design and training programs (Soproni, 2023). Comprehensive assessment of knowledge understanding, self-management skills, and generic skills concerning student employability help institutions customization their programs to better equip students for the labor market (Lamri & Lubart, 2023). Moreover, trends of employability over time provide apt timing for intervention strategies to be taken to improve student outcomes (Aldrup et al., 2022).

Appreciating employability works to the institutions' benefit and the learners' advantage. In identifying influences on employability, especially by pointing out influences such as social experience and training at work, educational programs offer specific support to learners. Proactively, this assists the graduates in developing relevant skills that promote their chances of finding employment shortly after graduation (Li et al., 2023).

Employability measurement instills a culture of continuous improvement for graduates (Cao et al., 2023). The globally integrated economy is rapidly changing through globalization and technological innovations, necessitating skills to be learned incrementally throughout a graduate's career. Schooling should, from their early point of entry, emphasize the issue of employability and thus nurture a lifelong learning attitude essential in today's dynamic world of jobs. Measuring the employability of college graduates one year after graduation is essential for evaluating education effectiveness, labor market needs, education policy development, graduate outcome improvement, and lifelong learning promotion (Donald et al., 2023). This multiple benefit is helpful to both graduates and ultimately strengthens the general framework of education by ensuring that it is constantly responsive to the changing demands of the workforce.

Clustering employability in various academic programs is essential for the day, as it enhances workforce alignment, improves educational outcomes, and fosters industry collaboration. Organizing educational offerings into clusters based on common characteristics and labor market needs helps educational institutions better prepare students for the realities of the job market.

Workforce alignment is one of the significant strengths of clustering employability because its educational offerings reflect the actual needs of the industry (Nylander & Holmer, 2022). In the context of changes in technology and economic environments, skills demanded by employers constantly change over time (Yang, 2021). A cluster approach helps an institution analyze specific skill requirements in high demand in such sectors. For example, it is shown that clusters engage more with workforce development, making education more responsive to real-market demand rather than an education-led approach (Zemmel et al., 2022). This alignment supports the development of the right skills among graduates, making them more employable.

Clustering also brings about improved performance in education through streamlined curriculum planning. Since curriculum development is geared to particular career tracks, teachers are more competent in designing curricula highlighting competencies most employers value (Hendricks et al., 2021). For instance, in the National Career Clusters Framework in the United States, education programs are categorized into 16 clusters, thereby assisting the students in making better career options and accordingly making choices that suit their interests as well as the economic needs of the market (Lupoae et al., 2023). This systematic approach, for one, enhances the level of engagement of a student and, at the same time, ensures that the oncoming graduates are equipped with the right kind of skills and knowledge to handle the chosen industries.

Another significant advantage of clustering employability is that it fosters cooperation among learning institutions and industrial stakeholders. Schools collaborate with businesses for more significant involvement through clusterings of programs by industry-specific groups; such collaborations most likely lead to internships, apprenticeships, and even job placement for students (Quew-Jones, 2022). Cluster initiatives undertaken by industry actors offer a variety of groundworks to students, preparing them for real-world challenges while also addressing the needs of companies. This collaboration benefits the companies as they source talent from a pool that meets the needs of their organizations.

Clustering employability addresses existing skills gaps between educational outcomes and employer expectations (Battisti & Maggio, 2022). Studies revealed that graduates report to the job market missing some of the most elementary skills, including emotional intelligence and hands-on skills (Rahman & Johari, 2022). In these clusters, emphasis is placed on educational institutions having opportunities to apply focused interventions that fill a portion of the gaps. For example, a framework for employability developed for business graduates revealed several dimensions of employability, including professional knowledge and generic competencies (Tong & Gao, 2022). Proper agglomeration of the respective competencies through the appropriate programs by the instructors ensures their better placement in graduates' employment (Hassad, 2010).

Clustering the employability of various academic programs is a critical step towards aligning education with labor market needs (Morozova, 2023), improving student outcomes, fostering industry collaboration, and addressing skill gaps. This strategic approach enhances the employability of graduates and, at the same time, contributes to a more responsive and efficient education system that matches the change in labor market demands (Javaid et al., 2023). Using cluster-based models, educational institutions form the spearhead in preparing students for careers and supporting economic growth.

The research covers and supports several of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, in this case, SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth). Looking at trend lines for colleges across programs regarding employability, the research directly goes to this arm of SDG 4.4 to ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults, both men and women, achieve literacy and numeracy. The interest of the study in detailing and strengthening employability outcomes aligns with SDG 8.6, which set a target to drastically reduce the share of youth not in employment, education, or training. This research outcome is realized through insights. It aligns education programs for labor market needs, indirectly supporting SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure in providing a competent workforce to fuel innovation and sustainable industrialization. Considering that this research is used to inform targeted interventions for improving employability, it fits SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) because it ensures equal opportunities for education and employment. The research aligns with SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals), focusing on the need for quality, in-time, reliable data to support decision-making in the higher education sector. This study, therefore, supports the holistic learning and working approach. On a more precise level, it supports the general vision of the UN in promoting sustainable development precisely because of an emphasis on quality education tied closely to economic prospects.

The primary research objective is to determine the trend of employability rates and total graduates within different college programs over the last three years, 2021-2023, using complex data analysis techniques applied to secondary data with DBSCAN clustering. Secondary data on employability outcomes within different academic programs are analyzed to reveal hidden structures and groupings of the programs studied. This exploratory analysis illuminates which programs are on similar trajectories or face challenges of similar proportions regarding graduate employment and informs strategic decision-making in higher education. The four objectives of this paper were to identify clusters of programs and their similarity in employability characteristics, detect outliers or programs with unique employability patterns, determine the stability or volatility of employability rates across varied fields of study, and generate data-driven insights that provide some guidance for targeted interventions to enhance student employability. This study relates to employment outcomes and supports evidence-based methods in curriculum development, career services, and planning in higher education.

Related Literature

The theory related to the measurement of employability one year after graduation from college comprises several frames of reference and models that help understand the complex nature of employability. The theories show the importance of skills, attributes, and external factors that impact a graduate's access to the job market.

One of the influential theoretical models is the Human Capital Theory, asserting that the skills and knowledge acquired through education and training increase human capital, making one more employable (Carlback et al., 2023). The more skills and qualifications a graduate acquires, the more chances there are to be employed, as the theory indicates. However, it is also acknowledged that academic credentials do not guarantee job placement, and graduates will be judged along other criteria, including practical skills and responsiveness to the job market. This is very relevant in light of

research on a significant skill gap between what graduates acquire in college and what employers want in the work arena.

The CareerEDGE model insists that, beyond the technical skills, the graduates should also embody soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and self-management (Yawson & Yamoah, 2023). Such a model underpins the engagement of these components as critical in developing outcomes in employability; as such, personal attributes and social experience contribute considerably to graduates' employability prospects, as highlighted by some studies.

The six dimensions of employability present another way to describe this concept by splitting down this abstract concept into human capital, social capital, personal attributes, personal behavior, perceived employability, and labor market conditions (Becker & Dorner, 2020). More importantly, this holistic view emphasizes that employability is more than an individual's skills; it also reflects external factors, such as networking possibilities and labor market dynamics. For instance, graduates with intimate social connections easily get connected to job openings and opportunities, which explains the interdependence of capabilities and conditions (Montano & Valdez).

Even with such contexts, employability assessments are complex, mainly because of the hegemony of numerous definitions and scales used in different contexts. There is no concurrence in opinion on suitable employability measures; hence, more standardized assessment instruments are called for (Montaño & Viado, 2024). For example, researchers have specifically designed scales to measure professional knowledge, generic competencies, and career management skills of employability. Those tools measure graduates' skills quantitatively against employers' expectations to give a clearer picture of graduates' readiness for employment (Montano & Utida, 2023).

Other theories have argued that students' perceptions of employability are essential to their job-seeking behaviors, considering that their attitudes toward their employability may determine what they do when seeking or applying for jobs. Attitudes might be influenced by reputation, the perceived quality of the university attended, and labor market conditions. Self-confidence is associated with proactive career management behavior, such as networking and seeking advice, to enhance employment opportunities (Petruzzello et al., 2022).

The theoretical climate surrounding the employability measurement among college graduates is complex and interplays individual capabilities and influences from external factors (Green et al., 2020). With holistic frameworks that consider personal attributes and contextual factors, there is a better chance that educational institutions would ensure that graduating classes have optimum transitions into workforce life (Taherdoost, 2022). This holistic approach aids in assessing current employability; simultaneously, it informs the design of improvement strategies for educational programs to meet labor market demands that evolve continuously (Bharambe et al., 2017).

Materials and Methods

This study used a quantitative, exploratory research approach to understanding patterns of employability rates of the different college programs. Secondary data analysis was used with unsupervised machine learning approaches, such as DBSCAN clustering, which unearth potential structures in employment data.

The analysis drew from secondary data garnered from the records of the institutional employer returns regarding college programs' employability rates and graduate numbers spread over three years, 2021 to 2023. The dataset included 26 unique programs in different colleges that provided general information regarding the directions in which employability was taking within the institution. This secondary data utilization lent a longitudinal perspective at no cost in terms of either time or resources, which usually accompanies the collection of primary data.

Before analyzing, data was pre-processed as follows: treated missing values as null where entries were considered "no info." Normalized employability rates Vary among different programs on different scales. Feature engineering introduced features like year-over-year changes in graduate and employability rates better to capture the year-over-year changes in graduate and employability.

DBSCAN was chosen as the first algorithm for the primary analytical method because it makes finding clusters of arbitrary shape feasible and insensitive to outliers. The values of the algorithm's parameter are obtained according to the following procedure: Dimensionality Reduction Principal Component Analysis (PCA). It was implemented to reduce the dimensionality of the data in question and retain its structure, thereby making direct visualization possible and improving the clustering algorithm's performance.

For selecting parameters, Epsilon (ϵ): The k-distance graph was employed to find a suitable ϵ value through this technique. That is done by plotting the kth nearest neighbor distance to each point, which is sorted in ascending order. For the graph, the "elbow" point was found where the distance was observed to increase steeply, and it leaned more towards an epsilon of 0.73. The MinPts: Minimum number of points in a dense region; set to 6 based on the general heuristic of using two dimensions for low-dimensional data. These metrics provided the clustering separation and cohesion in a quantified form with an understanding of the validity of the clustering solution. The clustering results were visualized by a 2D scatter plot of the first two principal components with points colored according to their assigned cluster. The methodology offers a robust framework for examining patterns of employability data across college programs, enabling researchers to gain insights into educational policy and program management implications.

Results and Discussion

Examining trends in employability for all college programs over the three years 2021 to 2023 in Table 1 reveals some interesting patterns and contrasting results. Architecture was relatively high and significant in employability percentage within the College of Architecture and Fine Arts Education, though it fluctuated and fell from 100% in 2021 to 87% in 2023. On the other hand, Fine Arts employability is entirely falling from 89% in 2021 to 50% in 2023; this shows a big problem in the job market for Fine Arts graduates.

Table 1. Employability of Programs SY 2021-2023

College	Program	Employability	2021	2022	2023
	Architecture	Total Number of Graduates	17	5	23

College of Architecture and Fine Arts Education		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	17	4	20
		Employability Rate	100%	80%	87%
	Fine Arts	Total Number of Graduates	9	3	2
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	8	2	4
		Employability Rate	89%	67%	50%
College of Computing Education	Library Information System	Total Number of Graduates	3	3	1
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	3	3	1
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	100%
	Computer Science	Total Number of Graduates	no info	16	24
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	no info	14	20
		Employability Rate		88%	83%
	Information Technology	Total Number of Graduates	10	96	104
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	10	88	101
		Employability Rate	100%	92%	97%
	Multi-Media	Total Number of Graduates	12	20	46
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	12	15	41
		Employability Rate	100%	75%	89%
	EMC-DA	Total Number of Graduates	5	2	6
		Employed w/in one year after graduation	5	2	no info
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	
	EMC-GD	Total Number of Graduates	1	4	1
		Employed w/in one year after graduation	1	4	no info
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	
College of Engineering Education	Civil Engineering	Total Number of Graduates	158	30	63
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	152	21	57
		Employability Rate	96%	70%	90%
	Chemical Engineering	Total Number of Graduates	15	8	1
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	13	8	1
		Employability Rate	87%	100%	100%
	Computer Engineering	Total Number of Graduates	18	28	8
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	11	12	7
		Employability Rate	61%	43%	88%
	Electrical Engineering	Total Number of Graduates	47	23	35

		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	42	23	30
		Employability Rate	89%	100%	86%
	Electronics Engineering	Total Number of Graduates	46	14	1
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	46	14	1
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	100%
	Mechanical Engineering	Total Number of Graduates	42	21	34
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	42	21	34
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	100%
	College of Criminal Justice Education	Criminal Justice	Total Number of Graduates	163	139
Employed w/in 1 year after graduation			163	139	15
Employability Rate			100%	100%	83%
College of Business Administration education	Business Economics	Total Number of Graduates	2	6	4
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	2	6	4
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	100%
	Financial Management	Total Number of Graduates	116	129	153
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	67	119.97	142
		Employability Rate	58%	93%	93%
	HR Management	Total Number of Graduates	64	71	85
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	34	64.61	64
		Employability Rate	53%	91%	75%
	Marketing Management	Total Number of Graduates	46	51	61
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	26	47.43	54
		Employability Rate	57%	93%	89%
	Legal Management	Total Number of Graduates	5	6	7
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	3	5.52	7
		Employability Rate	53%	92%	100%
	Real Estate Management	Total Number of Graduates	16	18	22
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	9	16.38	22
		Employability Rate	57%	91%	100%
College of Teachers Education	Education/Elementary Education	Total Number of Graduates	285	279	523
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	208	204	392
		Employability Rate	73%	73%	75%
College of Hospitality Education	Hospitality Management	Total Number of Graduates	27	17	66

		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	26	3	47
		Employability Rate	96%	18%	71%
College of Health Science Education	Nursing	Total Number of Graduates	41	11	63
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	14	10	34
		Employability Rate	34%	91%	54%
	Medical Technology	Total Number of Graduates	9	6	18
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	6	4	17
		Employability Rate	67%	67%	94%
	Nutritionist Dietician	Total Number of Graduates	2	3	4
		Employed w/in 1 year after graduation	2	3	4
		Employability Rate	100%	100%	100%

In general, the employability rates of the College of Computing Education were strong across all programs. Library Information System was impressive at 100% all three years. Information Technology and Multi-Media displayed high percentages in employability. IT improved from 92% to 97%, and Multi-Media rebounded in 2023 after a decline in 2022 to 89%. Computer Science maintained a percentage above 80%, with data available for only two years.

Engineering had a different tale. Civil Engineering and Computer Engineering proved strong, whereas the former rebounded from an abysmal year of 2022 at 90% this year, and the latter substantially increased its percentage to 88% from 43% in 2022. Mechanical and Electronics Engineering indeed had 100% employability during the last two years. While the Criminal Justice program within the College of Criminal Justice Education secured 100% employability for 2021 and 2022, it dropped to an impressive 83% in 2023, perhaps an outcome for further analysis.

Most programs improve or remain high from 2021 to 2023 in the Education of the College of Business Administration. Financial Management and Human Resource Management improved from 2021 to 2022 and remained stable, with a slight decline in 2023. Marketing Management also improved dramatically between 2021 and 2022 and remained the same in 2023. However, Real Estate Management improved from 57% in 2021 to 100% in 2023. The employability rate of the College of Teachers Education remained at around 73-75% for all three years of the Education/Elementary Education program. This attests to the continued demand for instructors in the teaching profession. In hospitality management of the College of Hospitality Education, volatility was high and plummeted from 96% to 18% in 2022 before partially recovering to 71% in 2023. This might be because of external factors and factors connected to tourism. Improving trends prevail in the College of Health Science Education: In Nursing, 34% for 2021, which improved to 91% in 2022 and fell to 54% in 2023. In Medical Technology, improvements went from 67% to 94% for the three consecutive years. The Nutritionist Dietician program has always had high employability ratings at 100%, but the number of graduates remains small.

This general view, while testifying to several programs that show repetitively very high percentages of employability, shows critical fluctuations and downturns for others,

testifying in turn to quite differential conditions in the labor market across the fields involved and probably outside interference of factors.

Figure 1 is a k-distance graph to assist in the choice of the correct epsilon value for the DBSCAN Clustering. Here, the x-axis plots the data points ordered by their distance to the fourth nearest neighbor. The y-axis plots that distance, and the blue line plots the sorted distances. The mean k-distance indicated here by the red dashed line is approximately 0.73. This graph shows that the curvature is relatively flat for most points but shoots up toward the end. The graph is used with a "knee" or knee point for calculating a valid epsilon value, serving as a threshold beyond which the distance to the fourth nearest neighbor dramatically increases. This estimate of epsilon appears on the cusp of the steeply rising curve, so most of the points are likely to bunch together with the rest of them as outliers or noise since their distance of increase is exceptionally high. With this choice of epsilon, the algorithm is leveled between significant cluster IDs and whether to identify outliers in a data set.

Figure 1. K-Distance Plot

In Table 2, the proposed parameters for DBSCAN clustering, an epsilon value of 0.73 and MinPts of 6, give insight into the data structure and the expected outcome. From the k-distance graph, the obtained epsilon value at 0.73 means how far the algorithm searches in each direction for neighborly points; therefore, it suggests that data clusters would be relatively dense and defined. The MinPts value of 6 means that a point will have at least six neighbors within the epsilon radius and, therefore, is classified as a core point of a cluster. In this combination of parameters, the algorithm appears set for compact, well-populated clusters but may miss sparser areas or separated points as noise. In either case, these settings strike a balance in identifying meaningful groups without over-segmentation of the data. They suggest that the amalgamation clusters formed by such mergers will likely be meaningful and coherent, displaying a reasonable tolerance of noise or outliers in the college program dataset.

Table 2. DBSCAN Parameters

Parameter	Value
Suggested Epsilon	0.73
Suggested MinPts	6

In Table 3, there is an interesting grouping of different college programs based on trends in employability. Three clusters have been isolated: -1, 0, and 1. The largest cluster was 0, with the number of programs equal to 19, while the smallest was cluster 1, with only two programs. According to most clustering algorithms, cluster -1 represents noise or outliers; in this case, it also contains five programs.

Table 3. DBSCAN Cluster Result

Program	2021	2022	2023	Cluster
Architecture	17	5	23	0
Fine Arts	9	3	2	0
Library Information System	3	3	1	0
Computer Science	46.36	16	24	0
Information Technology	10	96	104	-1
Multi-Media	12	20	46	0
EMC-DA	5	2	6	0
EMC-GD	1	4	1	0
Civil Engineering	158	30	63	-1
Chemical Engineering	15	8	1	0
Computer Engineering	18	28	8	0
Electrical Engineering	47	23	35	0
Electronics Engineering	46	14	1	0
Mechanical Engineering	42	21	34	0
Criminal Justice	163	139	18	-1
Business Economics	2	6	4	0
Financial Management	116	129	153	-1
HR Management	64	71	85	1
Marketing Management	46	51	61	1
Legal Management	5	6	7	0
Real Estate Management	16	18	22	0
Education/Elementary Education	285	279	523	-1
Hospitality Management	27	17	66	0
Nursing	41	11	63	0
Medical Technology	9	6	18	0
Nutritionist Dietician	2	3	4	0

Since there are 21 core programs, likely the ones in cluster 0 and 1-it is clear that most of them share some common trends relating to their employability. The core programs probably reflect similar patterns or degrees of employability over three years.

Interestingly, no border programs were found. Generally speaking, border programs refer to cases that fall at the cusp of any cluster, having common characteristics with several groups. As such, no border programs are found, meaning the clusters are relatively well-defined and distinct.

Five noise programs are associated with cluster -1. These programs do not belong very well in the central clusters; they have unique or highly variable employability patterns that distinguish them from others. This is due to volatility in employment markets, a significant variation in a program over time, or any other external factor affecting specific industries.

The Silhouette Score of about 0.399 goes a long way in telling the quality of the clustering. It ranges from -1 to 1, and the more positive this score is, the more well-defined the clusters will be. A score of 0.399 means that although the clusters have some structure, they are not that way and are not very well separated. This score is, therefore, moderate, meaning that while patterns are discerned in the trends across programs, there is still a fair amount of overlap or similarity between some of the programs from different clusters.

In short, this clustering result shows that, except for the few programs that suggest specific trends in employability (2 out of 26), most programs fall under one of their general trends, and many others have little to do with any given pattern. Therefore, although some common factors affect employability in most programs, unique dynamics are found across different fields of study. Further research about the characteristics of the clusters, particularly the outliers, informs practitioners on how they might better understand and improve employability rates for different academic programs.

Figure 2. DBSCAN Clustering of Program

Figure 2 reduced dimensional DBSCAN clustering results after the projection of the original data into a 2D space using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The first

principal component is shown on the x-axis, and the second is on the y-axis. The plot clearly shows three different clusters, one colored in teal representing cluster 0, one in yellow representing cluster 1, and purple representing cluster -1, which, most of the time in DBSCAN, represents noise or outliers. A tight clustering of points in the teal group near the origin indicates that these programs are similar. Two yellow points are slightly isolated from the main clumping; this suggests a small but very distinct group. The points in purple are spread across the plot, with some located significantly away from the central cluster, especially along the x-axis. This spread presents the fact that outlier programs are somewhat different from others. The points spread almost equally along both axes but mainly along the x-axis (PC1), indicating that the first principal component captures more data variance than the second.

The evaluation metrics in Table 3 provided information on the quality of DBSCAN clustering results on data for college programs. The Silhouette Coefficient is 0.3990, reflecting moderate cluster cohesion and separation. It is not high, but this score suggests that clusters are reasonably well-defined, and points are generally more similar to their cluster members than those in other clusters. A Calinski-Harabasz Index of 12.8237 strengthens the validity of the clustering found, as the more significant this number is, the more well-delineated the clusters are. At the same time, the score is not so great; hence, although there can be a structure in the data, the clusters cannot be very separate. The Davies-Bouldin Index is also 1.0487, complementing it with the fact that values as close to zero as possible testify to good clustering. The average similarity between the clusters is moderate: neither too low nor too high. Altogether, they point to a result of clustering that has some structural simplicity in the data but certainly is not well-separated or extremely compact in clusters. However, quite obviously, this is a condition that goes hand in glove with the nature of educational program data; indeed, clear distinctions among different groups of programs often do not exist at times due to overlapping characteristics or gradual transitions from one type of program to another.

Table 4. Evaluation Metrics

Metric	Value
Silhouette Coefficient	0.399
Calinski-Harabasz Index	12.8237
Davies-Bouldin Index	1.0487

Conclusion and Recommendations

Human capital theory proposes that education and training are investments that make the human being more productive and, therefore, more employed. The clustering of programs based on their employability rates and graduate numbers reflects the pattern of human capital development in different fields. Programs in the larger cluster with more stable employability rates might represent fields with more predictable education-employment outcome relationships. On the contrary, programs in the outlier cluster (-1) have unstable patterns and infer regions where the interaction between education and employment is more complex or subject to extraneous factors. This, therefore, offers a significant difference in the requirement to study sector dynamics when applying human capital theory to higher education and workforce planning.

The Career EDGE model lists experience, degree subject knowledge, generic skills, and emotional intelligence as the top for employability upgrading. The indirect reflection in the clustering results is that those programs maintaining a consistently high level of employability (like some in Cluster 0) could probably be hitting all these elements. A set of outlier programs (Cluster -1) with relatively variable outcomes are more sensitive to shifts in the expectations of the industries about their alumni or may require a reevaluation of the degree of their alignment with the elements of the Career EDGE components. For example, programs such as Information Technology, where there was a fair amount of growth, are doing an excellent job of responding to changes in industry needs - perhaps by increasing practical experience and updating subject matter knowledge.

The dimensions of employability-including Career Development Learning, Experience, Degree Subject Knowledge, Generic Skills, Emotional Intelligence, and Self-esteem/Self-efficacy-provide a framework to understand the multifaceted nature of employability. As such, the cluster results and the metrics of their evaluation point towards programs that differ in their emphases or success in other dimensions. Stable cluster (0) programs offer a balanced mix across these dimensions, leading to stable employability rates. The growing initiatives in Cluster 1 (HRM and MKTM) must be going very well in aspects such as Career Development Learning and Generic Skills that are most in demand in those business fields. The extreme programs in Cluster -1 are perhaps more prone to shifts in the industry's requirements, indicating that Experience or Generic Skills need more prominence.

The Silhouette Coefficient is average, standing at 0.3990, and the Calinski-Harabasz Index is also average, with a score of 12.8237, indicating that there are indeed discernible patterns in how programs differ along these dimensions but also with the presence of significant overlap. That goes with the concept that employability is complex and encompasses diverse factors, and the various programs achieve different balances within the six dimensions.

Thus, the clustering analysis shows a great diversity in employability outcomes across different college programs. Indeed, these outcomes are multifaceted, similar to postulations from the human capital theory, Career EDGE model, and six dimensions of employability. Most of the programs reveal some consistent pattern. However, other programs are more volatile in outcomes, so developing one-size-fits-all approaches to enhance employability outcomes is probably insufficient. Strategies should be aligned with program cluster characteristics and challenges while strengthening the field's most relevant employability dimensions.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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